

the metal ion. The C=O band at 1650 cm^{-1} in the ligand got shifted to 1600 and 1595 cm^{-1} in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes due to coordination. The band at 1540 cm^{-1} in the ligand was assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ph-C=C}}$ and the frequency was lowered to 1520 and 1500 cm^{-1} in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, respectively. The $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ band was observed in the complexes around 600 cm^{-1} .

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Dibenzyl Sulphoxide Complexes of Oxovanadate(II)

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SULPHOXIDES constitute a class of ambidentate ligand capable of being coordinated to metal ions through either oxygen or sulphur atom¹. Thus, they may act either as hard bases coordinating via oxygen, or as soft bases coordinating via sulphur. A large number of sulphoxides complexes of metal ions are known¹⁻³. In the present note, we wish to report dibenzyl sulphoxide (BzSO) complexes of oxovanadium(II). Dimethyl sulphoxide and diphenyl sulphoxide complexes of oxovanadium(II) are already reported in the literature⁴⁻⁶.

Experimental

Oxovanadium (VO^{II}) salts as starting materials were prepared by reported methods^{7,8}. The ligand

BzSO (Merck) was used without any further purification.

The preparation of the complexes involved the addition of an acetone or ethanol solution of a oxovanadium(II) salt to a solution of BzSO in the same solvent in required molar proportions. Some of the complexes crystallised immediately, while the others crystallised after concentration of the solution by passing dry air. The crystals were filtered off, washed several times with ethanol and finally with ether and dried in vacuum over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The physicochemical measurements were carried out as reported earlier⁹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) and the results of conductivity and molecular weight measurements reveal the molecular formula of the isolated metal complexes of BzSO as $\text{VOX}_2 \cdot 3\text{BzSO}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}, \text{NO}_3$ or NCS) and $\text{VO}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 5\text{BzSO}$. Except perchlorato complex, all the complexes are non-electrolytes. The perchlorato complex dissociates in PhNO_2 and behaves as a 1 : 2 electrolyte. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes lie in the range 1.78–1.84 B.M. These values correspond to one unpaired electron per vanadium(IV)¹⁰.

Partial ir data of the complexes are given in Table 1. S=O stretching frequency in free BzSO appears as a strong band at 1032 cm^{-1} (Refs. 11, 12), while in the spectra of all of its complexes, it has been observed in the range $960-945\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The other important absorption in the spectra of BzSO is the C-S stretching mode which has been identified in free ligand at 682 cm^{-1} . This band undergoes a slight positive shift on complexation. A negative shift of the S=O stretching frequency and a positive shift of the C-S stretching frequency are indications of the decrease in the double bond character of the S=O bond and an electron shift from the aryl group to the sulphur atom of the ligand. The data thus suggest a coordination from the oxygen atom of the sulphoxides. In far-ir region, $\nu_{\text{V-O}}$ has been identified⁴⁻⁶ (Table 1). The occurrence of a single medium intensity band for oxovanadium(II) stretching at $990-980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of a monomer V=O entity in all the complexes¹³. The absence of a ν_3 band of ionic nitrate (D_{3h}) around 1360 cm^{-1} together with the presence of bands at 1500 and 1305 cm^{-1} , due to the split ν_3 mode in the lower symmetry, indicate the covalent nature of the nitrate group^{14,15}. The two combination bands ($\nu_1 + \nu_4$) appear as weak bands at ~ 1740 and 1725 cm^{-1} . Application of the Lever separation method¹⁶ (the separation being 15 cm^{-1} in this case) suggests the monodentate nature of the nitrate groups. In thiocyanato complex, the presence of bands at 2050 ($\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$), 840 ($\nu_{\text{C-S}}$) and 475 cm^{-1} (δ_{NCS}) is normally associated with the terminal N-bonding thio group¹⁷. This is quite possible since vanadium(IV) is a typical hard

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NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PARTIAL IR DATA (cm⁻¹) OF DIBENZYL SULPHOXIDE COMPLEXES OF VOII

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol ⁻¹	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	$\nu_{\text{S-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{V=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{V-O}}$
	V	S	Anion					
BzSO	—	—	—	—	—	1 092vs	—	—
VO(BzSO) ₂ Cl ₂	5.95 (6.15)	11.32 (11.59)	8.39 (8.57)	4.2	821 (828)	950s	985m	440m
VO(BzSO) ₂ Br ₂	5.48 (5.56)	10.29 (10.46)	17.21 (17.44)	4.6	908 (917)	960s	990m	430m
VO(BzSO) ₂ I ₂	4.92 (5.04)	9.38 (9.49)	24.91 (25.12)	5.1	1 003 (1 011)	960s	980w	420w
VO(BzSO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	5.65 (5.78)	10.78 (10.89)	—	3.8	887 (881)	945s	990m	450m
VO(BzSO) ₂ (NCS) ₂	5.76 (5.84)	10.90 (10.99)	13.06 (13.28)	4.3	867 (873)	955s	980m	430m
VO(BzSO) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	3.49 (3.60)	11.19 (11.29)	13.86 (14.05)	52.9	1 465 (1 416)	950s	980m	440m

TABLE 2—THERMOANALYTICAL DATA OF DIBENZYL SULPHOXIDE COMPLEXES OF VOII

Compd.	Sample weight mg	Residual mass mg	Mass loss (%)				Residue (%) 550°	
			190–250°		290–390°		Theor. ^c	Exp.
			Theor. ^a	Exp.	Theor. ^b	Exp.		
VOCl ₂ ·3BzSO	24.9	2.46	41.66	42.86	83.33	85.18	10.99	9.87
VOBr ₂ ·3BzSO	23.6	2.16	37.62	39.49	75.24	77.04	9.92	9.15
VO(NO ₃) ₂ ·3BzSO	22.3	2.18	39.16	41.06	78.32	79.92	10.32	9.77
VO(NCS) ₂ ·3BzSO	20.1	2.01	39.51	41.22	79.03	80.12	10.42	10.00
VO(ClO ₄) ₂ ·5BzSO	21.4	1.28	48.72	50.27	81.21	83.02	6.42	5.98

^a Calculated for loss of 1.5 mol of ligand for chloro, bromo, nitro and thiocyanato complexes and 3 mol of ligand for perchlorato complex. ^b Calculated for total loss of ligand. ^c Calculated as V₂O₅.

acid¹⁸. In the ir spectra of VO(BzSO)₂(ClO₄)₂, the strong ν_3 and ν_4 bands appear at ~1 090 and 625 cm⁻¹, respectively, for the perchlorate ions, indicating that tetrahedral symmetry is maintained and the perchlorate ions are not bonded to the vanadium atom^{6,19}. In far-ir region, the medium intensity bands occur at ~320 and 240 cm⁻¹, which can be assigned as $\nu_{\text{V-Cl}}$ and $\nu_{\text{V-Br}}$, respectively. The ratio of $\nu_{\text{V-Br}}/\nu_{\text{V-Cl}}$ comes out to be 0.75 which is consistent with that reported²⁰ for six-coordinate complexes.

The electronic spectral bands of the VOII complexes are assigned to Ballhausen and Gray scheme²¹. Three *d-d* transitions are expected for six-coordinated complexes. The first band due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} ($b_2 \rightarrow e$) transition is observed around 12 000 cm⁻¹, while the second band due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ ($b_2 \rightarrow b_1$) transition is found around 16 000 cm⁻¹. The third band due to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$ ($b_2 \rightarrow a_1$) is expected around 28 000–26 000 cm⁻¹ and is not observed in the present complexes which is usually masked by the intense charge transfer bands occurring in the uv region⁶.

It is inferred from the data observed for these complexes that the vanadium(IV) appears to be six-coordinated and may have a distorted octahedral structure.

Thermal behaviour : Thermoanalytical results of the complexes are summarised in Table 2. The TG curves clearly indicate that the complexes are non-hygroscopic in nature and do not contain any water

molecules. There is virtually no change in weight upto 190°, but between this temperature and ~250°, a loss of 39.5–43% in weight is observed in halo, thiocyanato and nitrate complexes because of the loss of 1.5 moles of BzSO. In perchlorato complex, a loss of 50% in weight has been observed in this temperature range due to loss of 3 moles of BzSO. Finally at ~390°, all the BzSO molecules have been lost. The oxide V₂O₅ is formed at ~550°, following which there is no sensible change in weight.

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coefficient and n the number of electrons involved in reduction, have been evaluated by the modified method of Oldham and Parry⁶. According to these authors, the equation for an irreversible diffusion-controlled wave is

$$-E_{\text{dme}} = -E_{1/2} + \frac{2.303 RT}{\alpha nF} \log \left\{ \frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where, $x = i_E/i_{\text{lim}}$ (i_E = current at potential E , i_{lim} = limiting current) which is valid in the entire region $0 < x \leq 1$. From the plot of $-E_{\text{dme}}$ vs $\log \left\{ \frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right\}$, the values of $\frac{2.303 RT}{\alpha nF}$ and $E_{1/2}$ were evaluated from the slope and intercept, respectively. Polarographic characteristics are presented in Table 1. For a completely irreversible cathodic

Polarographic Behaviour of Gallium(III) in some Disubstituted Pyridines

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THE reduction of gallium(III) at d.m.e. has been studied in presence of some complexing organic reagents by only a few workers¹⁻³. In the present note, we describe the reduction of gallium(III) at d.m.e. in presence of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP).

Experimental

Details of the polarograph and the experimental technique have been described in earlier communication⁴. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.054 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at zero V (vs S.C.E.) in 0.1 M NaClO₄, $h = 40 \text{ cm}$.

Solutions of DHP and AHP (Aldrich) were prepared in water. Solution of gallium(III) was prepared by dissolving the metallic gallium in perchloric acid. Mixture of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate (pH 3.0) was used as supporting electrolyte. A 0.01% gelatine was used as the maximum suppressor. Polarograms were recorded for solutions containing $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ Ga^{III} ion and varying amounts of DHP or AHP as the case may be alongwith 0.1 M NaClO₄, HClO₄ (pH 3.0), and maximum suppressor at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

From the nature of the polarograms and the $E_{1/2}$ values it has been found that reduction of gallium(III) occurred in a single three-electron irreversible and diffusion-controlled step. Half-wave potentials and αn values, where α is the transfer

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Ga^{III} IN PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF DHP AND AHP LIGANDS

Ga^{III} = $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M NaClO}_4$, pH = 3.0, Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, 0.01% gelatine

System	Ligand mM	$-E_{1/2}$ (V vs S.C.E.)	αn	$\alpha n E_{1/2}$
Ga ^{III}	0.0	1.289	—	—
Ga ^{III} —DHP	2.0	1.382	0.39	0.036 8
	4.0	1.386	0.38	0.036 8
	6.0	1.390	0.365	0.036 9
	8.0	1.393	0.36	0.037 4
	10.0	1.395	0.36	0.038 1
Ga ^{III} —AHP	2.0	1.377	0.39	0.034 3
	4.0	1.381	0.38	0.034 9
	6.0	1.384	0.37	0.035 1
	8.0	1.387	0.37	0.036 3
	10.0	1.389	0.365	0.036 5

process it may be shown that

$$i/(i_d - i) = 0.886 (t/D)^{1/2} k^0 \frac{\beta_K [L]^K}{\beta_N [L]^N} \quad (2)$$

where, t is the drop time in seconds, D diffusion coefficient in $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, β_K and β_N are the stability constants of K and N species and $[L]$ is the concentration of the ligand, k^0 the rate constant in $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. If the equilibrium favours the predominance of the highest complex, the equation (2) reduces to

$$\frac{d \log i/(i_d - i)}{d \log [L]} = K - N \quad (3)$$

It was found that the differential of the righthand side in both the cases is the same. Hence, it could be concluded that in both the cases same species suffers reduction at the d.m.e. Complex formation on addition of the ligand was indicated by the change in the half-wave potential, $\Delta E_{1/2}$, ($E_{1/2}$ of Ga^{III} in DHP or AHP - $E_{1/2}$ of Ga^{III} in the supporting electrolyte alone) of the metal ion. The values of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ could be used for comparing the stabilities of complexes found. But in case of irreversible electrode processes, the half-wave potential also depends upon the transfer coefficient, α . A comparison, therefore, could be made only for the values corresponding to the same values of α . Alternatively $\alpha n E_{1/2}$ instead of $E_{1/2}$ could be used⁵.

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